

EFFECT OF GRAPHENE NANOPATELETS FEATURES ON CURE KINETICS OF BENZOXAZINE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The influence of graphene nanoplatelets (GNP) on the cure kinetics and rheokinetics of a benzoxazine resin has been studied. Two types of thermally reduced graphene oxide nanoplatelets with different thickness, lateral dimension and purity degree were used to reinforce the benzoxazine matrix. The kinetic and rheokinetic studies reveal that the addition of graphene has a catalytic effect in the cure reaction of the resin, decreasing the peak temperature, activation energy and gel time, and increasing the reaction rate constant k . Despite the different morphological features of the two types of graphene used, no significant differences have been observed in benzoxazine nanocomposites with the same content of GNPs.

1 INTRODUCTION

Benzoxazines are thermosetting resins that have been recently introduced in the aircraft industry as an alternative to bismaleimide resins for FST (fire-smoke-toxicity) applications. The currently used bismaleimides are expensive in terms of material and processing conditions (high temperature and long curing time) [1]. However, the cure temperature of benzoxazine resins is similar to that of epoxy. This materials exhibits excellent properties as near-zero volumetric change upon curing, low water absorption, high char yield, a low coefficient of thermal expansion, an easy thermal curing by ring opening polymerization and, for some benzoxazines, the glass transition temperature (T_g) might be higher than curing temperature [2].

In recent years, polymer/graphene nanocomposites have widely attracted the interest of researchers in order to improve the thermal, mechanical and electrical properties of polymers. This is because graphene, a one-atom thick sheet of sp^2 - hybridized carbon atoms, has a superior Young's modulus (1 TPa), tensile strength (130 GPa), and an exceptional thermal ($5300 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$) and electrical (up to $6000 \text{ S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$) conductivity [3, 4]. Compared with carbon nanotubes (CNTs), graphene has a higher surface-to-volume ratio and is much cheaper, which make it more suitable as nanofiller in polymers [5]. Several studies have been directed to enhance the properties of epoxy resin by the addition of graphene, but only few works have been developed with benzoxazines. Zeng et al. [6] reported the curing behaviour and thermal properties of graphene oxide/benzoxazine and achieved an increase in thermal stability and chard yield of these nanocomposites, while Alhassan et.al [7] have checked that the addition of graphene oxide caused a premature ring opening of benzoxazine which causes a decrease in glass transition temperature.

Up to now, much effort has been focused on the curing kinetics of thermoset resins to improve the understanding of their curing behaviour and mechanism. When nanofillers are introduced in a thermoset polymer, they can induce, retard or catalyse the cure reaction of the matrix, so the curing characterization and kinetics of nanocomposites produced with graphene and benzoxazine have to be deeply studied. In this work, the effect of two different graphene nanoplatelets on cure behaviour of benzoxazine/graphene nanocomposites is appraised using different models by curve fitting on DSC (differential scanning calorimetry) results. Moreover, rheological test were performed in order to determinate the viscoelastic properties of the nanocomposites and how the addition of graphene affects to growth of the infinite molecular network (gelation).

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

A benzoxazine-based resin supplied by Henkel Corporation has been used for this study (density 1.2 g/m³). This resin is intended for use as matrix in carbon fibre composites manufactured by infusion techniques, such as Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) and Liquid Resin Infusion (LRI).

Two different types of graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) manufactured by thermal reduction were purchased to Avanzare (Avangraphene-2) and XG-Sciences (xGnP® Graphene Nanoplatelets, Grade M, 15 μ) and their main features are shown in Table 1.

Graphene identification	Supplier	Purity (%)	Average flake thickness (nm)	Specific surface area (m ² /g)	Average particle lateral dimension (μ m)	Oxygen content (%)
Gr-Xg	XG-Sciences	99.5	< 6	120-150	15	<1
Gr-Av	Avanzare	95	< 2	*	20	0.5-1.5

*Not indicated in the data sheet

Table 1. Graphene nanoplatelets features

2.2 Preparation of nanocomposites

The composites were manufactured by using a three roll calender EXAKT 80E (Exakt Advanced Technologies GmbH, Germany). The dispersion process was carried out in seven steps and the gap between rolls was changed between 120 μ m to 15 μ m [8] with the aim of accomplishing a mixture in which graphene was exfoliated and uniformly distributed. Afterwards, the mixture was degassed in vacuum at 100°C for 15 minutes and the cure cycle suggested by the supplier of benzoxazine resin was carried out. The cured samples were allowed to cool to room temperature inside the oven. Nanocomposites with different amounts (0.5 wt.% and 2 wt.%) and type of graphene (Gr-Xg and Gr-Av) were prepared and named: BzGr-Xg-0.5, BzGr-Av-0.5, BzGr-Xg-2 and BzGr-Av-2 respectively.

2.3 Characterization

X-Ray diffraction of graphene (XRD) was measured with a X'Pert PRO diffractometer from Panalytical, using Cu K α ($\lambda = 1.5406$ Amstrong) radiation source operated at a voltage of 45 kV and 300 mA of electric current. The diffraction patterns were recorded from 10° to 80°. Along with XRD, Raman spectra were obtained by using a Horiba Jobin-Yvon HR800UV spectrometer with a 632.8 nm excitation wavenumber He-Ne laser. Morphological characterization and the dispersion degree of the GNP/benzoxazine nanocomposites were also done by Transmission Optical Microscopy (TOM).

The curing kinetics were studied by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) experiments performed in a TA Instruments Q2000 calorimeter with N₂ as purge gas. The samples were placed in aluminum pans and hermetically sealed. The dynamic tests on uncured samples were carried out at the heating rates of 2, 5, 10 and 15°C/min in a temperature range from -50°C to 330°C. After this first heating run, the sample was cooled to atmosphere temperature and a second heating was conducted at

10°C/min to check for the complete cure. For the isothermal experiments, the samples were placed in the cell at 25°C and the temperature was then quickly raised to the selected value for each isothermal experiment (170, 180, 190, 200 and 210°C). When the baseline level was reached again after the exothermic peak, the samples were cooled to atmosphere temperature and a second heating was carried out to 330°C in order to determine the residual heat of curing reaction.

Rheokinetic analysis was performed with an AR-G2 rheometer from TA Instruments, using a 25 mm parallel plate assembly in oscillation mode. Isothermal tests (170, 180, 190 and 200°C) were carried out for a fixed frequency of 1 rad/s. The variation of the viscoelastic properties during cure, such as storage modulus (G'), loss modulus (G'') and complex viscosity (η^*), was recorded as a function of reaction time.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Graphene characterization

The quality of GNPs was analyzed using XRD and Raman spectroscopy. Figure 1 shows X-ray diffraction patterns of both types of graphene sheets. A strong peak was detected at $2\theta \sim 26.6^\circ$ corresponding to a d -spacing of 0.335 nm which is close to the graphite d -spacing. The presence of this peak allows confirming that graphene materials are not in an oxidative state and not all GNPs have been exfoliated. The Scherrer equation [9] is generally used to obtain the average crystalline size defined as average domain size information from broadened X-ray diffraction lines. As it can be observed in XRD patterns, the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of (002) is larger for Gr-Av which means a higher number of graphitic layers [10]. The peak at $\sim 55^\circ$ corresponds to the reflection of graphitic planes (004), confirming that graphene nanoplatelets are not completely exfoliated.

The Raman spectroscopy provides structural and electronic information of graphene nanoplatelets. Figure 2 shows the spectra of Gr-Xg and Gr-Av, where the D-band peak at $\sim 1340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, the G-band peak at $\sim 1590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and the 2D-band peak at $\sim 2700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are observed [11]. The D peak (sp^3 -hybridized carbons) is known as the disorder band and its presence indicates defects or edges in the graphene sample. The intensity of this band raises when dangling bonds percentage in plane terminations increases and it is also related with the oxidation degree and purity of the sample. It can be clearly appreciated a higher intensity D-band for Gr-Av which means a great number of defects in this graphene type. The G peak is due to the bond stretching of all pair of sp^2 atoms in a 2-dimensional hexagonal lattice. Judging from the higher intensity and lower peak width of G-band for Gr-Xg, it seems to have a more regular graphene structure than Gr-Av [10, 12].

Figure 1. X-Ray diffraction patterns of graphene nanoplatelets.

Figure 2. Raman spectra of graphene nanoplatelets.

3.2 Morphological characterization of nanocomposites

The dispersion of graphene nanoplatelets in benzoxazine resin has been evaluated with TOM. A small drop of suspension was placed on the glass slide and a cover slip was put on it. Figure 3 shows transmission optical micrographs of nanocomposites with 2 wt.% of both types of graphene before and after three roll calendaring process. It can be clearly observed that before dispersion process BzGr-Av-2 has much bigger aggregates of GNP than BzGr-Xg-2 (see Fig. 3a). After these mixtures were subjected to calendaring, the size of these black clusters in benzoxazine matrix become smaller, however GNP aggregates in BzGr-Av-2 continued having, in general, a higher size that in BzGr-Xg-2. It suggests that the exfoliation degree of graphene nanoplatelets seems to be highly improved for the nanocomposites with the graphene of XG-Sciences.

Figure 3. TOM micrographs of GNP/benzoxazine nanocomposites: (a,c) BzGr-Av-2, (b,d) BzGr-Xg-2, before (upper row) and after (lower row) three roll calendaring process.

3.3 Dynamic cure kinetics

The dynamic DSC curves obtained from the cure reaction of neat resin and its nanocomposites with a 0.5 wt.% and 2 wt.% of both types of graphene at heating rate of 10°C/min are shown in Figure 4, and the total heat of reaction (ΔH), onset cure temperature (T_{onset}) and peak temperature (T_p) in Table 2 (all values of enthalpy were normalized to the neat amount of resin in the nanocomposite mixtures). It can be observed that the reaction enthalpy slightly increases with the addition of graphene and this increase is more pronounced in the nanocomposites with the graphene supplied by XG-Sciences, while the onset and peak temperatures decreased when the amount of graphene is higher. The same tendency was observed in the experiments with heating rates of 2, 5 and 15°C, so it seems that the addition of graphene has a catalytic effect in the curing of benzoxazine. These resins cure via ring-opening polymerization [2]. Residual functional groups in the reduced graphene can act as weak organic acid which accelerate the oxazine ring opening, as it was previously reported by Zeng et al. [6]. This can explain the catalytic effect of graphene nanoplatelets in the cure reaction.

Figure 4. Dynamic DSC curves at a heating rate of 10°C/min for neat resin and its nanocomposites.

Sample	ΔH (J/g)	T_{onset} (°C)	T_{peak} (°C)
Neat resin	434.9	237.5	248.5
BzGr-Av-0.5	446.1	237.4	248.4
BzGr-Xg-0.5	451.4	236.2	247.6
BzGr-Av-2	443.3	236.9	247.7
BzGr-Xg-2	458.4	218.5	245.5

Table 2. Results obtained from 10°C/min tests on neat resin at its nanocomposites

The DSC thermograms at all heating rates for neat resin are showed in Figure 5. As the heating rate increases, the exothermic peak for both benzoxazine and its nanocomposites shifts to higher temperatures. Zeng et al [6] have reported the same behavior in benzoxazine nanocomposites with graphene oxide. The average total exothermic reaction heat of neat benzoxazine is 440.1 J/mol. This value was also calculated for GNP/benzoxazine nanocomposites because it was used to determine the extent of cured reached in isothermal tests.

Figure 5. DSC thermograms of neat benzoxazine at different heating rates (2, 5, 10 and 15°C/min).

Variation of exothermic peak temperature with heating rate can be used to extract information about cure kinetics. In this work, three kinetic methods commonly used for thermosetting polymers were employed in order to determine the activation energy (E_a): Kissinger, Ozawa and the isoconversional method of Flynn-Wall-Ozawa (FWO) [13]. With these non-isothermal methods the activation energy of the cure reaction can be quantified without knowledge of reaction mechanism. In Table 3 values of activation energy calculated by these three methods are listed. In contrast to Kissinger and Ozawa methods, the isoconversional method assumes that activation energy is a function of the extent of cure (α), so the value showed in the table is the average of activation energy at particular conversions of $\alpha= 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$ and 0.9 . Obtained average value of activation energy for neat resin was 92.4 kJ/mol, which is consistent with data found in the literature [13, 14]. Besides, it is noted that for all nanocomposites a slight reduction in E_a with the introduction of graphene was observed. The lower activation energy, the more easily the cure reaction can occur. The decrease in the activation energy barrier is also accompanied by an increase in cure enthalpy values with the addition of the filler, supporting the supposition that graphene has a catalytic effect in the cure reaction of benzoxazine.

Sample	E_a (kJ/mol)			Average E_a (kJ/mol)
	Kissinger	Ozawa	FWO	
Neat resin	88.4	92.1	96.5	92.4
BzGr-Av-0.5	85.0	88.8	92.5	88.8
BzGr-Xg-0.5	85.8	89.6	91.8	89.0
BzGr-Av-2	86.0	89.7	91.3	89.0
BzGr-Xg-2	86.3	90.0	91.1	89.1

Table 3. Activation energy obtained by using the Kissinger, Ozawa and FWO methods

3.3 Isothermal cure kinetics

For thermosetting polymers, the curing process is commonly described by kinetic equation:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T) \cdot f(\alpha) \quad (1)$$

where $f(\alpha)$ is the kinetic model and $k(T)$ the reaction rate constant which is dependent on temperature and it is usually assumed to follow the Arrhenius temperature dependence. For autocatalytic thermosetting resin systems the following equation has been commonly applied:

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^m \cdot (1 - \alpha^n) \quad (2)$$

where n and m are kinetic exponents of the reaction and their sum represents the overall reaction order. The reaction rate ($d\alpha/dt$) of the system can be obtained from the above equations:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T) \cdot \alpha^m \cdot (1 - \alpha^n) \quad (3)$$

As previously mentioned, isothermal experiments were carried out for every sample at 170, 180, 190, 200 and 210 °C. The conversion (α) and the reaction rate ($d\alpha/dt$) against time at 190°C for all samples were plotted in Figure 6 and Figure 7a, respectively. The conversion curves have an inflexion point when plotted versus time and the maximum reaction rate was not reached at time zero which confirms the autocatalytic nature of benzoxazine and its nanocomposites polymerization reaction. In Figure 7b the reaction rates as function of conversion for the neat resin and its nanocomposites are showed. The time at which maximum reaction rate was reached is shorter in graphene-doped samples than neat benzoxazine but no significant changes were found in the conversion value at this reaction rate (Table 4). A similar situation was found in results obtained at other isothermal cure temperatures.

Figure 6. Conversion as a function of cure time for the neat resin and nanocomposites at 190°C.

Figure 7. Reaction rate as function of time (a) and conversion (b) for the neat resin and its nanocomposites at 190°C.

Sample	$(d\alpha/dt)_{\max}$	
	t (min)	α (-)
Neat resin	29.03	0.40
BzGr-Av-0.5	28.60	0.39
BzGr-Xg-0.5	28.48	0.40
BzGr-Av-2	27.99	0.41
BzGr-Xg-2	26.24	0.38

Table 4. Time and conversion reached at maximum reaction rate at 190°C.

In order to determine the kinetics parameters (k , m and n), a non-linear regression fit based on the Lavenberg-Marquardt method was applied to equation (3). The obtained values at 170, 190 and 210°C are exhibited in Table 5. The constant rate naturally increases with the increase in cure temperature for all samples, and k also showed an increase when the amount of graphene in the sample is higher. The reaction order ($m+n$) was around 3.0 at temperatures above 190°C which is in agreement with the values reported by Ran et al. [14] in their study about a RTM benzoxazine resin, where $m+n$ was between 2.5-3.2.

Sample	T_{cure} (°C)	α_{\max} (-)	k (min ⁻¹)	m	n	$m+n$
Neat resin	170	0.82	0.26	1.52	3.26	4.78
BzGr-Av-0.5		0.80	0.33	1.73	3.57	5.30
BzGr-Xg-0.5		0.81	0.33	1.64	3.71	5.35
BzGr-Av-2		0.79	0.34	1.66	3.76	5.42
BzGr-Xg-2		0.83	0.34	1.64	3.54	5.18
Neat resin	190	0.93	0.45	1.34	2.08	3.42
BzGr-Av-0.5		0.92	0.58	1.50	2.39	3.89
BzGr-Xg-0.5		0.92	0.52	1.44	2.23	3.67
BzGr-Av-2		0.92	0.60	1.50	2.48	3.98
BzGr-Xg-2		0.92	0.56	1.46	2.48	3.94
Neat resin	210	0.99	0.90	1.21	1.85	3.06
BzGr-Av-0.5		0.99	0.92	1.24	1.84	3.08
BzGr-Xg-0.5		0.99	0.89	1.23	1.97	3.20
BzGr-Av-2		0.99	0.92	1.24	2.00	3.24
BzGr-Xg-2		0.99	0.98	1.24	2.10	3.34

Table 5. Values of k , m , n and overall reaction order for benzoxazine and its nanocomposites at 170, 190 and 210°C.

3.4 Rheokinetic analysis

One of the most important changes due to the material curing is gelation. Gelation occurs at a well-defined and often calculated stage in the course of the chemical reaction and it is an irreversible transformation from a viscous liquid to an elastic gel, which marks the first appearance of the infinite network [15]. In this study, rheological measurements at different isothermal temperatures (170, 180, 190 and 200°C) were carried out in order to evaluate, on the one hand, the effect of graphene addition in gelation time (t_{gel}) and, on the other hand, if any difference between the two types of graphene is observed. Two different criteria were used to determine the t_{gel} : the intercept of storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') and the onset of the normal force (F_{onset}) and the obtained results were compiled in Table 6.

A simple calculation of the activation energy of the gelation can be performed from gelation time data obtained at different temperatures. The relationship between the activation energy and gelation time can be described by the following expression:

$$\ln t_{gel} = a + \frac{E_{gel}}{R.T} \quad (4)$$

where t_{gel} is the gelation time at the isothermal temperature, E_{gel} is the apparent activation energy, T is the curing temperature, R is the the universal gas constant and a is a temperature dependent constant. By lineal fitting of experimental data of t_{gel} (calculated as the intersection of storage modulus and loss modulus) at each isothermal temperature to equation (4), the values of E_{gel} for each sample were calculated and the results obtained are shown in Table 7.

The gelation time decreases with the addition of graphene being this reduction more pronounced when Gr-Xg graphene is added. As the same time, the activation energy for gelation also decreases, especially for BzGr-Xg-2 nanocomposite. Both early gelation times and lower activation energies for GNP/benzoxazine nanocomposites indicate that reaction occurs more quickly. This tendency is more marked for the nanocomposites with the graphene supplied by XG-Sciences.

Sample	T _{cure} (°C)	t _{gel} (min)	
		G'-G'' intercept	F _n _{onset}
Neat resin	170	63.0	66.6
BzGr-Av-0.5		59.2	60.4
BzGr-Xg-0.5		59.4	60.9
BzGr-Av-2		59.5	59.6
BzGr-Xg-2		49.4	47.8
Neat resin	180	37.2	37.7
BzGr-Av-0.5		37.8	35.3
BzGr-Xg-0.5		36.9	34.3
BzGr-Av-2		36.0	32.7
BzGr-Xg-2		32.5	30.9
Neat resin	190	24.0	20.8
BzGr-Av-0.5		21.2	20.1
BzGr-Xg-0.5		22.2	19.1
BzGr-Av-2		23.4	25.8
BzGr-Xg-2		19.4	16.2
Neat resin	200	12.0	10.1
BzGr-Av-0.5		11.6	10.2
BzGr-Xg-0.5		12.1	10.1
BzGr-Av-2		11.9	-
BzGr-Xg-2		10.7	9.4

Table 6. Gelation times for benzoxazine at its nanocomposites at several isothermal temperatures by different methods.

Sample	E _{gel} (kJ/mol)
Neat resin	94.15
BzGr-Av-0.5	95.11
BzGr-Xg-0.5	91.88
BzGr-Av-2	91.46
BzGr-Xg-2	88.85

Table 7. E_{gel} for neat benzoxazine and its nanocomposites with different amount and type of graphene.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Two different types of graphene nanoplatelets with different dimensions and purity have been added to a benzoxazine resin. The XRD and Raman spectroscopy analysis have revealed that the graphene supplied by Avanzare has more defects and a higher number of layers than that of XG-Sciences. The dispersion process in the resin with three roll calender clearly reduces the size of agglomerates with the two types of graphene, but they larger in general in the nanocomposites with Gr-Av.

Despite the different morphological characteristics of the two graphene nanoplatelets used, they have similar effect on the cure reaction of the benzoxazine resin. The results of the cure kinetics reveal that the addition of graphene has a catalytic effect which can be due to residual acid groups that act as weak organic acid, accelerating the ring opening polymerization of benzoxazine resin. This agrees with the decrease in the gelation time and activation energies.

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